

AGENCY IN THE LIFE COURSE OF CRIMINAL OFFENDERS

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There has been an increasing interest in the concept of agency in the life course, and theorists in this area have added been adding substantially to our understanding of the subject. The study of agency in the life course provides a set of tools that allow a finer analysis of how people plan and guide their actions. A thorough analysis of agency in the life course of criminal offenders does not seem to have been done using some of the newer conceptualizations that have been developed. This paper represents an attempt to examine how agency works to guide the lives of criminal offenders over the course of their lives. This is an important endeavor, as it is difficult to change behavior when one does not understand how or why behavior occurs.

Emirbayer and Mische (1998) suggest that agency is “a temporally embedded process of social engagement, informed by the past (in its habitual aspect), but also oriented toward the future (as a capacity to imagine alternative possibilities) and toward the present (as a capacity to contextualize past habits and future projects within the contingencies of the moment)” (p. 963). Their conceptualization recognizes several facets of agency. Agency involves choice. Choices are made in the present moment, based upon current events, but also take past experience and visions of the future into consideration. Agency involves interactions with others and shapes the direction of the life course. Agency is an iterative process that occurs over time, and involves both continuity and change.

Many theorists have addressed the subject of agency in the lives of criminal offenders, and have developed theories that explain some aspects of offender agency, but existing theories are not accurate in their conception of agency. For instance, Cornish

and Clarke (1986) contend that criminal behavior is a “rational choice”, with criminals deciding to commit crimes after weighing the pros and cons of their actions. This is true, but agency is not quite as simple as they propose. Choices are often irrational, suggesting that the processes involved go beyond logic. Gottfredson and Hirschi (1990), in their “General Theory of Crime”, argue that crimes are more likely to be committed by people with deficits in their capacity to choose rational behavior options. This is also true, but they fail to take the full effects of agency in people’s lives into account, and tend to ignore how small decisions in the present can have big effects over the life course. Without a complete understanding of agency, it is difficult to understand how these two theories can both be true. How can a person be both rational, and irrational, at the same time? To begin to understand, one must first understand how decisions are made.

The Decision Making Process. The logical decision is subjectively perceived as a cognitive process, in which a person weighs the pros and cons of various actions, and then makes a rational decision calculated to produce the optimal outcome. The problem with this conceptualization is that people are often irrational. When this fact was pointed out to a co-worker, he noted that this was why advertising executives on Madison Avenue make such high salaries. Advertisers are able to appeal to the irrational and emotional facets of people. The irrationality of the person becomes clear in the case of the criminal offender. Criminal offenders repeatedly make choices that cause great harm to both themselves and others. The choices offenders make are often perceived as incomprehensible, both to themselves and others. In order to understand the decisions of the offender, a more complete understanding of the decision-making process is required.

The Role of the Brain in Making Decisions. Decisions are made in people's brains, which have evolved in order to enhance the probability of survival of as many genetically similar organisms as possible (Dawkins, 1976). Brains are massively parallel biochemical computers that work, through a variety of electrical and chemical processes, to sort, filter, and process information from the environment in order to enhance survival and production of other organisms with a similar genetic code. The brain sums all of the inputs from the senses, along with memories of past experiences, visions of the future, and inputs from each of the separate brain mechanisms, in order to produce actions designed to optimize the survival potential of the organism.

An understanding of the multidimensional operation of the brain is required in order to fully understand the decisions that are produced. Brains are aggregate mechanisms with many individual parts that work together in a "Society of Mind" (Minsky, 1988). Sometimes one part of the brain is more important in the decision making process than at other times. The net result is a tendency toward survival.

The more significant brain systems involved in making decisions have been identified through neuropsychological research done by Gray (1970) and expanded by Gray and McNaughton (2000). They found that people have three main neuropsychological systems in their brains that work together to produce or inhibit behavior. These three systems, a Fight, Flight, Freeze System (FFFS), a Behavioral Approach System (BAS), and a Behavioral Inhibition System (BIS), work together to help people decide which action to take in any given situation. The functioning of these three systems is an important factor in criminal behavior.

The Process of Agency. Emirbayer and Mische (1998) conceptualize agency as a three-part process that involves iteration (past experiences), projectivity (visions of the future), and practical evaluation (weighing the options in the present moment). All three processes are important parts of agency and work together to produce action.

Iteration involves “the selective reactivation by actors of past patterns of thought and action, as routinely incorporated in practical activity, thereby giving stability and order to social universes and helping to sustain identities, interactions, and institutions over time.” (p. 971). Emirbayer and Mische point out that people can only attend to a small portion of the information available at any time, and that attention is directed to those items that have been found to be significant in the past.

While the consideration of possible behaviors is informed by behaviors that have worked in the past, there is also a projective element that involves expectations for the future. Possible actions are played out in the mind through a number of processes, which include anticipation, narrative construction, hypothesis construction, and experimental enactment of possible actions in the imagination.

The practical evaluation element of agency involves a number of elements. There is often uncertainty in the possible outcomes of action. Based upon past experience, and desires for the future, the mind must work to identify and categorize the information available in order to determine the most relevant schemas. This process involves a period of deliberation. Once the possible choices are brought to mind, a decision can be made, which will then lead to action. The quality of the decision and resulting action are dependent on past decisions, the ability to project oneself into the future, and the ability to evaluate, decide, and act.

Criminal Behavior. An understanding of criminal behavior is not possible without understanding what criminal behavior is. Criminal behavior and deviance are subsets of rule breaking behavior. In the case of criminal behavior, the rules are codified by society into laws, and in the case of deviance, the rules are either implicitly or explicitly specified through societal norms. Rule breaking behavior, or cheating (Tooby, & Cosmides, 1992), is a behavioral strategy that produces reproductive benefits in a society based upon cooperation. In other words, criminal behavior has evolved as a mechanism to enhance the probability of survival for individuals under certain circumstances. To argue that it is dysfunctional is to belie the fact that many criminals are very successful at creating multiple offspring with similar genetic profiles.

Rule breaking behaviors are behaviors that anyone is capable of, under the right circumstances. This was pointed out by Durkheim (1895) who argued that “crime is normal”. Crime may be normal, but it is much more normal for some than others. There is a wide disparity in the variety, severity, amount, and rate of criminal behavior over the course of people’s lives (Blumstein, et. al., 1986). Crime is especially prevalent during adolescence and young adulthood (Quetelet, 1831/1984; Hirschi & Gottfredson, 1983). As Moffitt (1993) pointed out, criminal behavior and deviance during adolescence is more normal than no criminal behavior. The distribution of criminal behavior also varies significantly between individuals. Wolfgang, Figlio, and Sellin (1972) found that 10% of juveniles in the Philadelphia birth cohort were responsible for more than 50% of the crimes committed. The reasons for the differences in inter-individual and intra-individual rates of offending over the life course are many and varied. At the heart of these differences are differences in the abilities of the criminal offender to exercise agency.

The Criminal Act. For a criminal act to occur, several factors must come together at the same time. Opportunity theorists, Cohen and Felson (1979), have developed a model of offending which indicates that predatory offending occurs when a suitable target, a capable and motivated offender with criminal inclinations, and a lack of a capable guardian are present. Without these factors, offending does not occur.

Crime requires a suitable target. Targets may be sought out, or they may appear randomly. Data collected by Zamble and Quinsey (1997), in interviews of criminal offenders, reveals that most offenders do not think about committing crimes before the act. The level of forethought varies by offense, with 92% of assaults, 70% of robberies, and 88% of property offenses listed as not being planned beforehand (p. 109). These results indicate that many criminal acts are associated with chance events.

Crime requires a capacity for the criminal act. Criminal capacity can be affected by physical, intellectual, emotional, and structural factors. For instance, small children and geriatric citizens have little physical strength, and are thus precluded from committing certain types of crimes; many people do not have the knowledge required to commit some crimes; many people would not be emotionally capable of stabbing someone; and shooting someone, or breaking into a safe, is not possible without the proper tools. Crimes are simply not possible without the capacity to commit them, and this places a limit on the commission of crimes.

Crime requires motivation on the part of the offender. Motivation varies from moment to moment, and is affected by the strength of the needs, desires, and goals of the offender. The importance of needs cannot be overstated in developing an understanding of agency. For instance, an adolescent with a stomach full of watermelon will probably

not be found in the watermelon patch stealing watermelon to eat. That same adolescent may be in the watermelon patch stealing watermelons to smash. The motive for action has an impact on the type of crime committed.

Crime requires criminal inclinations. Some people are simply more inclined to commit criminal acts than others. The reasons for the differences in the propensity to commit crimes include agitated emotional states, drugs or alcohol in the body, weak or ineffective social bonds (Hirschi, 1969), certain personality traits (Gottfredson, & Hirschi, 1990), neurological deficits (Moffitt, 1990), and traumatic brain injuries (Amen, 1998). There is also strong evidence that suggests that the timing of brain development results in a period in the life course where most people a greater capacity and motivation to commit crimes.

Crime requires the absence of a capable guardian. Most people simply will not commit crimes if someone is there to stop them. This fact is probably one of the strongest arguments for the importance of agency in criminal behavior. Nothing forces people to commit crimes, because if it did, people would have to commit crimes when the armed guard was there to stop them.

Factors Affecting the Propensity to Offend. Criminal behavior is the result of a number of causes, and this fact may be comprehended more fully by observing the large number and wide variety of criminology theories (Vold, Bernard, & Snipes, 2002). Each theory of criminal behavior explains some aspect of the decision to offend. From the standpoint of agency, the causes of criminal behavior may be broken down into temporary, persistent, and developmental categories. These categories are somewhat

arbitrary, as most crimes are usually a result of all three factors, but they provide a useful lens for examining the level of agency that is possible for an individual offender.

Agency in Desistance From Crime

The importance of agency in desistance from crime has been the subject of debate. Sampson and Laub (1993) have argued that decisions to join the military, get married, or find employment have created turning points in the life courses of offenders that have led to desistance from crime. Hirschi, & Gottfredson, (1995) claim that the turning points simply reflect the effects of “self selection and statistical regression” (p. 137). They suggest that apparent changes in people who get married or find a job are an “illusion” (Hirschi, & Gottfredson, 1993: 51).

The arguments of Hirschi and Gottfredson are based on a number of assertions that they have made over the years. In their General Theory of Crime (Gottfredson, & Hirschi, 1990), they contend that criminal behavior is due to low self-control on the part of the offender. They suggest that low self-control is the result of poor parenting practices, and rank order differences in self-control are stable between individuals over the life course. In effect, people with lower self-control than others at age ten will have lower self-control than others at any other age. The fact that some offenders with seemingly identical levels of self-control desist from crime, while others persist in offending could be due to hidden differences in self-control. They argue that the only way to really tell if certain experiences help people desist would be to conduct randomized experiments, where people were assigned to groups who either got a treatment, or didn't get a treatment. Since random assignment to military and marriage

are difficult, if not impossible, there is no way to determine whether agency had anything to do with their seemingly beneficial effects.

Developmental Trajectories of Agency. The most significant factor in the variability of the commission of criminal acts, both between and within individuals, is due to the changes that occur in the capacity for agency in the human organism over the life course. People start out in life with almost no ability to exercise agency. A capacity for agency develops as they mature, and each person develops the capacity for agency to a different extent and at a different rate.

Brain Development. The brain does not start out in a fully functional form. The process of brain development involves a continual process of adaptation and change through the production of new brain cells and an increase in connections between brain cells, as well as a destruction of brain cells and a pruning back of connections between brain cells. While the process of brain development continues over the entire life course, there are certain times, particularly in infancy and adolescence, that the brain experiences more rapid change. The type and timing of experiences become significant factors during these periods, and certain experiences are necessary at certain times if the brain is going to be able to work at maximum potential.

The capacity for agency is affected by biological and cognitive factors, as well as past experience. The development of the biological capacity for agency is well documented and is a function of development in the pre-frontal cortex and other areas of the brain. The brain continues to develop over much of the life course before experiencing declines in performance in old age. A meta-analysis of neurological studies

by Romine and Reynolds (2005) demonstrated that the pre-frontal cortex is still developing at a steady pace at age 22. Bartzokis et. al. found evidence that areas of the brain are developing through age 50 and then declining after that. People also develop greater cognitive capacity for understanding the moral implications of their actions as they age, as demonstrated by Kohlberg (1994).

The fact that agency is increasing throughout most of the life course has important implications for studies of criminal behavior. Gottfredson and Hirschi (1990) have developed a construct, which they call low self-control that is an appropriate construct for describing a lack of capacity for agency. They have proposed that people who commit have low self control “tend to be impulsive, insensitive, physical (as opposed to mental), risk-taking, short-sighted, and non-verbal” (p. 90). Restated, criminals act rashly, without caring about the consequences for others, act without thinking, tend to be fearless, take very little thought for the future, and don’t talk much. These factors tend to indicate a lack of agency.

There is empirical support for Gottfredson and Hirschi’s theory. Pratt and Cullen (2000) did a meta-analytic analysis of research on the connection between low self-control and criminal behavior and found that there was a mean effect size of .257 between attitudinal measures of low self-control and criminal behavior, and a mean effect size of .277 between behavioral measures of low self-control and criminal behavior. These results indicate a substantial association between low self-control and criminal behavior, and by extension, a lack of agency and criminal behavior.

Given that a lack of agency is associated with criminal behavior, and the brain is becoming more capable of agency throughout the years up to age 50, one would expect

that crime would decline during that period. This is not exactly the case. The aggregate age-crime distribution, called the age-crime curve, was documented by Quetelet (1831) in an analysis of the arrest rates in France in the 1800s, and has since been found to fairly similar in its overall shape across many time periods and cultures (Farrington, 1986; Goring, 1913; Hirschi, & Gottfredson, 1994; Neison, 1857). The age-crime curve actually shows a sharp increase in the level of crime for individuals from 10 to 17 years of age, which would not make sense if an increase in the capacity for agency was related to a decrease in crime. After 17, crime rates do decline as expected, with a fairly steep decline from 17 to 30; followed by a gradual decline over the next decades, which results in few offenders in their 50s and 60s arrested for crimes.

Age Crime Curve

Trajectories of Aggressive Behavior. There would appear to be something else happening in the life course to explain the lack of association between agency and crime. Research by Nagin and Tremblay (1999; Tremblay, 2000) sheds some light of the problem. The trajectory of violent physical behavior appears to peak at about age two for the majority of people and start declining from there. The declining trajectory of violence was demonstrated by in a series of studies. Tremblay also found, using cross-sectional data from the National Longitudinal Survey of Children and Youth (NLSCY), which is a random sample of 16,038 Canadian children aged four to 11 years, that indirect aggression (hurting someone without physical aggression) appears to rise over the years as direct physical aggression subsides. Tremblay notes that adolescents are credited with much more violent acts, but this is attributed to greater capacity for creating physical harm due to increased strength of the aggressor during adolescent and young adulthood.

These results show that agency is increasing over the life course for most people, but a small minority do not experience a very large increase in agency, resulting in flat trajectories of violent behavior through childhood. This study suggests that two factors are at work to produce a certain level of crime. The capacity for crime is increasing during childhood and the capacity to stop crime is also increasing.

If a variable rate in the growth of agency is assumed, indicating a reduction in the potential for crime, and a fairly stable rate in the growth of strength through childhood, followed by a leveling off of strength in middle adulthood, and a decline in strength in later life, the plot of the capacity for crime due to strength, and the plots of the reductions in the capacity due to agency would look as it does in Figure 1.

Figure 1

Strength Curve (Capacity for Crime) vs. Three Levels of Agency

These plots demonstrate that if agency grows throughout the life course, and agency is negatively associated with criminal behavior, then criminal behavior would increase in childhood until about 17, and then drop off after that.

Trajectories of Criminal Behavior. Criminal behavior has a beginning, and also ends for most people as they move through the life course. Uggen and Pilavian (1988) argue that the causes of crime are different from the causes of desistance from crime. Both processes will be considered in this article. It will be argued that agency plays an important, but somewhat different role in either case.

Brain Dysfunction. Most brains are able to do their jobs fairly well, as evidenced by the success of the human race in its replication efforts. Some brains however, become

dysfunctional, and have difficulty making optimal decisions. This is often the case with the criminal offender. Brain dysfunctions can either be structural, or procedural. Some of the causes of structural dysfunction, and the symptoms related to those brain dysfunctions, were documented by Daniel Amen (1998), who performed thousands of brain scans of people with behavioral problems. He found five main areas of the brain where over-activity, or under-activity, were associated with significant behavioral problems. He suggests that some of these dysfunctions may be alleviated through the administration of drug therapy. Procedural dysfunctions are the result of cognitive distortions of reality. Procedural dysfunctions may be reversed when the cognitive distortions are removed.

An understanding of the FFFS is needed in order to understand some types of offender behavior. While the BAS and BIS operate in normal ranges of emotion, the FFFS operates in times of danger. When people get emotionally agitated, the FFFS kicks in and their ability to make decisions is substantially compromised. When a person is sufficiently agitated, they enter a state characterized by Elum and Elum (2003:283) as a “non-thinking zone”, where rationality is substantially diminished. Some offenders have neurological and cognitive deficits

Pleasure and Pain. The brain typically measures survival potential by creating an estimation of the likelihood that an action will produce either pleasure or pain. Experiences that provide pleasure are perceived as enhancing survival, and experiences that produce pain are perceived as threats to survival. The brain works to increase pleasure, and reduce pain. When there is an opportunity to increase pleasure or reduce

pain, and there is a capacity to realize that opportunity, the brain will act upon that opportunity if there is sufficient motivation and a lack of inhibitory factors. An understanding of these four factors then provides an understanding of criminal behavior.

An examination of the empirical research tends to support several of the positions taken by Gottfredson and Hirschi, with criminal offenders often experiencing difficulty in making rational choices, but some of the arguments they have made are not supported by the existing research. Since their theory provides a basic framework for an understanding of agency in the life course of criminal offenders, it will be used as a starting point for discussion.

An examination of the topic of agency, as described by Emirbayer and Mische, reveals that agency is almost the exact opposite of low self-control. Research has tended to support the position taken by Gottfredson and Hirschi.

Choices are always made in the present, but they may involve habitual patterns of behavior and be influenced by future goals and dreams. The issue of choice in the commission of criminal and deviant acts has been hotly debated, with one set of theorists (Gottfredson, & Hirschi, 1990), and another set of Both of these positions reflect a misunderstanding of the process of agency in criminal behavior. Agency is the means by which people guide their lives through the possible pathways in life, and is always present. Agency is a complex, often irrational, process that involves a continuous interplay between action and reaction in the course of existence.

Agency is present in any human behavior, but it is not as well understood in the case of criminal behavior. Part of the problem may be a misunderstanding of the nature of criminal behavior. People look at the lives of the criminal offender and wonder why

anyone would choose to live such a life. The risk of injury and incarceration are high, and the rewards appear to be insignificant. An understanding of criminal behavior must examine the processes involved in the decisions to act, and must look at the rewards of the behaviors involved.

The Decision Making Process

Several branches of science inform our understanding of agency in the life course, and each contributes to an overall understanding of how choices are made. At the biological level, we know that

Brain Mechanisms Involved in Decision Making. Agitated Emotional States.

The FFFS system points to possible mechanisms involved with aggression. The relationship between emotional state and offending has not been actively studied, but evidence that emotions are involved with aggression was found by Canter and Ioannou (2004), who report that annoyance, anxiety, and anger are the emotions most often reported as occurring during the commission of violent acts or murder.

Weighing the Options. Both the psychological literature and the literature on agency provide insights into the decision making process. Work by Janis and Mann (1977) is in agreement with the BAS/BIS conceptualization of approach/avoidance. They suggest that the possible benefits and risks of each possible action are considered in a type on mental balance sheet before action is taken.

From Input to Action.

The Decision to Commit Crimes

Opportunity theorists, Cohen and Felson (1979), argue that predatory offending occurs when a suitable target, a capable and motivated offender with criminal

inclinations, and a lack of a capable guardian are present. Their argument is similar to the rational choice arguments of Cornish and Clarke (1986), who suggest that the offender weighs the pros and cons of taking action before committing a criminal act. In both theories, the external and internal factors are considered before action is taken.

For the most part, the decision to offend is similar to other decision-making processes, which means that both approach (BAS) and avoidance (BIS) systems are involved in the process. Opportunity, potential rewards, possible risks, offending capacity, past experience, present state of mind, and motivational factors, such as goals, needs, and desires are all factors in the decision to offend. An issue that is unique to the decision making process of criminal offenders, is possible problems in the functioning of the BAS/BIS systems. There is a considerable body of evidence suggesting that the ability to make decisions is compromised in one or more of the decision-making systems in criminal offenders. These problems can occur in the FFFS, BAS, and/or the BIS systems. The following sections provide an examination of some of the factors involved in the decision to commit criminal acts, along with an examination of possible deficits in the decision making systems.

Factors Involved in the Decision to Commit Crimes

Opportunity. Opportunity is often overlooked in theories of criminal behavior. This is not without justification. The randomness of opportunity does not diminish its importance in an understanding of the agency involved in criminal behavior however, because without the opportunity to commit a crime, crime could not occur. It must also be noted that even though the percentages are small, some criminal offenses are planned and thought out before they are committed.

Capacity for Offending. The capacity for criminal offending varies significantly over the life course. Capacity can include physical, intellectual, emotional, and structural factors. For instance, small children and geriatric citizens have little physical strength, and are thus precluded from committing certain types of crimes; many people do not have the knowledge required to commit some crimes; many people would not be emotionally capable of stabbing someone; and shooting someone, or breaking into a safe, is not possible without the proper tools. Crimes are simply not possible without the capacity to commit them, and this places a limit on the commission of crimes.

Motivation. Motivation is a function of needs, desires, and goals. All three are important factors in criminal behavior. Needs have been categorized by Maslow (1943) as physiological (food, water, air, clothing, etc.), safety (personal and financial security, health and well-being, etc.), love (friendship, intimacy, etc.), esteem (respect from others, self-esteem, self-respect, etc.), and self-actualization (becoming all that we are capable of becoming). These universal needs are important factors in the commission of crimes. Crimes are more likely when needs are not met, and less likely when needs are satisfied.

Behavioral Activation System Deficits

One of the issues for criminal offenders is that they often have needs that are felt more strongly than in most people. For instance, many offenders have a high need for stimulation. This need can develop due to neurological deficits that result in a much stronger need for stimulation in order to achieve a comfort level (Amen, 1998).

Criminological theories vary in the level of the importance placed on motivation for explaining criminal behavior. Some theories place a major emphasis on motivation and others ignore the subject. Strain theorists (Agnew, 1992; Cloward and Ohlin, 1960;

Cohen, 1955; Merton, 1938) argue that crime is a result of frustrated needs and desires. Control theorists (Gottfredson, & Hirschi, 1990) argue that everyone has frustrated needs and desires, and yet most people do not commit crimes. This may be true, but some people may experience frustration in a different way than others. The differences in frustration level may create a differential impetus for criminal activity.

Behavioral Inhibition System Deficits.

The lack of sufficient behavioral inhibition in criminal offenders is a major factor in the commission of criminal acts. The differences in levels of inhibition have a variety of causes, which include both temporary and persistent factors, and this fact must be understood if an understanding of criminal behavior is desired. The causes of a lack of sufficient inhibition to prevent criminal behavior The individual factors affecting inhibition will be discussed first, followed by a discussion of developmental factors.

Agitated Emotional States. When people get extremely agitated, their ability to make decisions is substantially compromised. If a person is sufficiently agitated, they enter a state characterized by Elum and Elum (2003:283) as a “non-thinking zone”, where rationality is essentially non-existent. The relationship between emotional state and offending has not received much attention in the literature. Canter and Ioannou (2004) report that the emotions most often reported, as occurring during the commission of violent acts or murder, are annoyance, anxiety, and anger.

Drugs or Alcohol in the Body. The correlation between drug and alcohol use and criminal activity is strong. Miller and Welte (1986) found that 60% of offenders reported using drugs or alcohol before committing the offense they were arrested for. The reasons for this high correlation are not completely clear, but Steele and Josephs (1990) report

that, the primary mechanism that contributes to problems experienced while consuming alcohol is a reduction of inhibition that occurs while intoxicated.

Weak or ineffective Social Bonds. Hirschi (1969) found that criminal behavior in adolescents is associated with weak bonds to society.

Personality Traits That Lead to a Reduction in Inhibition. There is a considerable body of evidence that criminal offenders are more likely to have low self control, which has been defined by Gottfredson and Hirschi (1990) as being “impulsive, insensitive, physical (as opposed to mental), risk-taking, short-sighted, and non-verbal” (p. 90). Pratt and Cullen (2000) did a meta-analytic study of research on self-control and found a moderate correlation between low self-control and criminal behavior. The mean effect size was .257 for the relationship between attitudinal measures of self-control and criminal conduct. Caspi et. al. (1994) assessed the personalities of almost 2000 adolescents in new Zealand and Pittsburg, and found that people with low constraint and high negative emotionality were significantly more likely to report multiple delinquent acts, have repeat convictions, or be convicted for violent offenses. Stewart and Rowe (2000) found that offenders released from prison were much more likely to be rearrested within one year if they lacked direction, had poor conflict resolution, were impulsive or thrill seeking, had poor conflict resolution or poor regard for others, had low frustration tolerance, were unrealistic in their goal setting, were non reflective, had poor problem solving skills, or were unable to generate choices. These results all point to a diminished capacity for people who commit criminal and deviant acts to make choices.

Neurological Deficits. Moffitt (1990) reviewed the literature and found a high correlation between neurological deficits and the commission of criminal acts.

Traumatic Brain Injuries. An event in the life course of many criminal offenders that is receiving increased attention is the occurrence of a severe head injury. A study using a random sample (over 5000 people) drawn from five U.S. communities found that 8% of respondents reported a major blow to the head, leading to unconsciousness or confusion, at some point in their lifetime (Silver et. al., 2001). Silver et. al. report that people with head injuries were more than twice as likely to have alcohol or drug abuse problems, and four times more likely to attempt suicide. The incidence of head injuries in a jail and prison populations is from four to ten times higher than in the normal population. Slaughter, Fann, and Ehde (2003) found the incidence of head injuries in a jail population varied from 29% of inmates responding reporting a severe head injury to 87% reporting some form of head injury. These results provide evidence that some offenders may experience a deficit in decision making ability due to brain injury.

Several attempts have been made to provide randomized studies. Maruna (2001) found that subjective accounts of desistance from criminal behavior by ex-offenders indicate that agency is involved in the desistance process. Maruna created a quasi-experimental situation by matching two groups of offenders, one persisting in crime, and one desisting, for prior criminality. He conducted interviews of both groups and found that offenders desisting from crime could point to decisions they made to stop offending.

Zamble and Quinsey (1997) found that recidivists and non-recidivists had substantial differences in their thought patterns. Recidivists tended to think more about prison, criminal acts, money, drugs, and alcohol, and non-recidivists thought more about their jobs and self-improvement, and had more positive thoughts (p. 83). These results indicate that agency, in the form of selective attention, is involved in desistance.

Continuity and Change in Offending

One problem that has perplexed criminology theorists is the problem of continuity and change in offending. Some people continue to commit crimes over time and some desist from crime. A high percentage of criminal offenders that are committing crimes at one age are usually committing crimes at another age. This facet of offending may be due to the concept of bounded agency that was developed by Shanahan and Hood (2000).

There is evidence for bounded agency in the life courses of offenders. Once an offender has a criminal record, it is more difficult to find employment. Pager (2003) found that people with a criminal record were called back for interviews at less than half the rate of people with no criminal record. This means that the state of being an offender makes it harder to become a non-offender. Incarceration also has an effect on future earning potential. Western (2002) found that wages for people who experienced incarceration were 10% lower than those who weren't incarcerated.

The concept of bounded agency is present in the theory of cumulative disadvantage developed by Sampson and Laub (1997). Research by Nagin and Paternoster (1991) indicates a strong correlation between present criminal behavior and future criminal behavior. Sampson and Laub suggest that there structural impediments in the criminal justice system that inhibit desistance from crime.

Bounded agency may play a part in the persistence in crime due to structural impediments that offenders face when they leave prison. Travis (2002) writes about the problem of "invisible punishment" that occurs as offenders exit prison. Ex-offenders often have no money, no job, and no place to live. They have few pro-social friends and many anti-social friends. These factors make the decision to not reoffend a difficult one.

Agency in Desistance From Crime

The importance of agency in desistance from crime has been the subject of debate. Sampson and Laub (1993) have argued that decisions to join the military, get married, or find employment have created turning points in the life courses of offenders that have led to desistance from crime. Hirschi, & Gottfredson, (1995) claim that the turning points simply reflect the effects of “self selection and statistical regression” (p. 137). They suggest that apparent changes in people who get married or find a job are an “illusion” (Hirschi, & Gottfredson, 1993: 51). They argue that the only way to really tell if certain experiences help people desist would be to conduct randomized experiments, where people were assigned to groups who either got a treatment, or didn’t get a treatment. Since random assignment to military and marriage are difficult, if not impossible, there is no way to determine whether agency had anything to do with their seemingly beneficial effects.

Maruna (2001) created a quasi-experimental comparison by matching two groups of offenders, one persisting in crime, and one desisting, for prior criminality. He conducted interviews of both groups and found that offenders desisting from crime could point to decisions they made to stop offending.

Subjective accounts of desistance by ex-offenders also indicate that agency is involved in the desistance process. Zamble and Quinsey (1997) found that recidivists and non-recidivists had substantial differences in their thought patterns. Recidivists tended to think more about prison, criminal acts, money, drugs, and alcohol, and non-recidivists thought more about their jobs and self-improvement, and had more positive thoughts (p. 83). These results indicate that agency is involved in desistance.

Recommendations for Future Research on Agency

The literature on agency gives us a better understanding of the mechanisms involved in decision-making. This opens the door to the possibility of developing methods to enhance the capacity for agency in offenders who lack such capacity. It also provides insights into why people decide to do what they do. Through those insights, it may be possible to affect decisions made so that more pro-social options are made.

There is evidence that agency can be already be enhanced through various forms of treatment. A review of past studies was done by Aos, Miller, and Drake (2006), and they found that there were a variety of effective offender treatments. The most effective targets for treatment were infants, through home health programs for mothers, adolescents, through foster care programs, the mentally ill, and sex offenders.

There has been research suggesting that agency is important in the cessation of drug addiction and other problem behaviors. Prochaska and DiClemente (1992) have found five stages of change, pre-contemplation (not thinking about changing), contemplation (thinking about changing), preparation, action, and maintenance. The role of agency is important in each of these five stages and also in the processes of change that people use to navigate the stages. The decisional balance model of Janis and Mann (1977) is a key part of their theory. Decisional balance matches the practical evaluation portion of the agency model developed by Emirbayer and Mishe. Decisional balance theory states that there are approach and avoidance factors in each available option, and all must be weighed before action is taken. Self Efficacy (Bandura, 1997) is also a key element of the theory, since action is often not contemplated when the likelihood of success is low.

Therapy methods have been developed to enhance the movement from pre-contemplation to contemplation, preparation, and action. The most notable is the motivational interviewing method of Miller and Rollnick (2002), which is designed to help build cognitive dissonance between the present self and the ideal self. Therapists also work to enhance self-efficacy through social modeling by providing examples of people who have successfully changed.

The enhancement of agency must reflect that offenders may have different goals and dreams than non-offenders. Ward (2002) argues that treatment providers should not impose their normative values upon offenders, and that the “good life” is different for everyone. Ward’s theory is consistent with the work on intrinsic motivation done by Deci and Ryan (2000). Deci and Ryan have found the externally imposed goals and objectives are not carried out as well as internal goals and objectives. This is important work in the area of offender agency.

Concluding Remarks

The subject of agency is an important topic in criminology. Past treatments of the subject of offender motivation and decision-making tend to ignore some facets of agency and focus on others. This practice sets the field back significantly because research results are suspect when they do not account for the heterogeneity of criminal offenders in the capacity for agency, and in the values and motivations of the offender. Future efforts need to look at how agency develops over the life course, treatments that enhance agency, and methods for changing behavior that work to enhance the offender’s existing pro-social goals and dreams.

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